

ULTRAVIOLET-C (UV-C) TREATMENT FOR EXTENDING SHELF-LIFE OF RED CHILLI (*Capsicum Annum L.*)

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ABSTRACT Red chilli (*Capsicum annum L.*) is widely consumed in Malaysia but is prone to rapid postharvest deterioration due to high moisture content, resulting in weight loss, disease incidence, and shortened shelf life. The objective of this study was to evaluate the effect of different durations of Ultraviolet-C (UV-C) treatment in extending the shelf life of red chilli. A total of 75 chillies were subjected to five treatments: T0 (no treatment), T1 (3 minutes), T2 (6 minutes), T3 (9 minutes), and T4 (12 minutes) under 254 nm wavelength. Chillies were stored at room temperature (24°C) for 12 days. At 3-day gaps, four characteristics were monitored which are soluble solid content (SSC), firmness, weight loss, and disease incidence. The results showed that UV-C treatment affected all measures, however not all adjustments were statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). T1 had the least weight loss and disease incidence, whereas T4 retained most firmness. This study highlights UV-C's potential as an environmentally safe, non-chemical preservation strategy for red chilli postharvest storage.

Keywords: postharvest, disease incidence, soluble solid content, weight loss, fruit firmness

1. INTRODUCTION

Red chilli (*Capsicum annum L.*) is an essential vegetable in Malaysian cuisine. Since its spoilage, postharvest losses are popular, mostly due to microbial decomposition, water loss, and chilling harm in cold storage. Recent research highlights UV-C as a promising method to reduce microbial activity and extend shelf life without chemical residues [1]. This study explores the effectiveness of various UV-C exposure durations on preserving the postharvest quality of red chillies stored at room temperature.

2. MATERIAL AND METHOD

A Completely Randomized Design (CRD) was used five treatments with 15 replicates each: T0 (control), T1 (3 minutes), T2 (6 minutes), T3 (9 minutes) and T4 (12 minutes) of UV-C exposure at 254 nm. Chillies were stored at room temperature (24°C) for 12 days. Statistical analysis was performed by using one-way ANOVA. Data was collected at days 0, 3, 6, 9 and 12, focusing on firmness (kgf), weight loss, soluble solid content (°Brix) and disease incidence.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Firmness

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Figure 3.1 Clustered bar mean chart showed the firmness (kgf) during the storage

All treatments showed a gradual reduction in firmness over time. T4 maintained relatively higher firmness values on day 12, indicating delayed tissue softening due to longer UV-C exposure. However, it showed no statistically significant differences across all treatments and storage days.

2. Weight Loss

Figure 3.2 Clustered bar mean chart showed the weight loss during the storage

T1 (3 min) recorded the least cumulative weight loss suggesting improved moisture retention on day 12. However, no significant differences ($p > 0.05$) were observed among treatments.

3. Soluble Solid Content

Figure 3.3 Clustered bar mean chart showed the soluble solid content (SSC, °Brix) during the storage °Brix values fluctuated across the storage period. On day 12, T3 is significantly higher than T4. While the others share the same letter hence not significant even though the value is higher. This is potentially due to dehydration concentration effects.

4. Disease Incidence

Figure 3.4 Clustered bar mean chart showed the disease incidence during the storage

T1 and T3 exhibited lower visual fungal infections compared to the control (T0), supporting UV-C’s antimicrobial effects as reported in previous literature [2][3].

4. TABLE, IMAGE AND FIGURE

Figure 1 UV-C machine

Figure 2 Chillies treated under UV rays

5. CONCLUSION

This study concludes that UV-C exposure, particularly at low doses (3–6 minutes), has the potential to extend the shelf life of red chilli by reducing weight loss and disease incidence while preserving firmness and SSC. UV-C treatment offers a non-chemical, eco-friendly alternative for postharvest preservation. Further studies should investigate the synergistic effects of UV-C with other packaging technologies.

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